

Solar-Driven Hydrogen Production using a BODIPY Covalent Organic Framework Hybrid Photocatalyst

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ABSTRACT: The search for photoactive materials able to efficiently produce solar fuels is a growing research field in the current energy crisis. Here, we report the synthesis and characterization of an enamine linked COF based on BODIPY (IEC-1). This COF is used as a platform to prepare TiO₂-based hybrid photocatalysts for solar driven hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Remarkably, this hybrid system has been scaled up and evaluated in a solar reactor at semi-pilot plant scale. The optimized hybrid IEC-1@T-10 photocatalyst, containing 10 wt.% COF loading, achieved 2.9-times higher photonic efficiency than bare TiO₂, and even surpassed by 6.5-times the lab-scale performance, in the absence of any noble metal co-catalyst. This system, shows also a high stability without deactivation during three sunny days. The secret of the hybrid's success lies on its high photostability. This interesting behavior is mainly due to the synergy between inorganic and organic semiconductors that lead to a 3-fold increase in the electron-hole (e⁻/h⁺) pairs lifetime, compared to bare TiO₂, in good agreement with a type II charge transfer mechanism.

KEYWORDS: covalent organic frameworks, BODIPY, hybrid, photocatalytic H₂ production, charge transfer mechanism, transient absorption spectroscopy, solar reactor.

■ INTRODUCTION

In response to the current energy demand, artificial photosynthesis (AP) has emerged as a sustainable alternative to the use of fossil fuels.¹ AP systems are able to efficiently capture and convert solar energy and then store it in the form of chemical bonds.² Solar energy is therefore used to split water and produce hydrogen, and/or to transform carbon dioxide and water into a renewable source of energy-rich carbon-containing products.³

Conventionally, inorganic semiconductors such as metal oxides and chalcogenides have been the most widely studied materials for this purpose.⁴ However, we are witnessing a renaissance of organic based semiconductors due to the description of more robust materials like graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄),^{5,6} conjugated porous polymers (CPPs),⁷ metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)^{8,9} and covalent organic frameworks (COFs)¹⁰⁻¹⁵ as photocatalyst.

Thanks to their tunable pore size, low density, structural periodicity and on demand chemical functionalization, COFs have been widely applied in areas such as gas storage and separation,^{16,17} heterogeneous catalysis,¹⁸⁻²¹ energy storage and optoelectronic devices.²²⁻²⁴

In 2014 Lotsch *et al.* reported for the first time the use of a hydrazone-based COF as photocatalyst for H₂ production in presence of Pt as cocatalyst.²⁵ This successful study initiated the exploration of COF-based photocatalysts in the whole community and the publications in this area has acutely increased in the last decade.¹⁰ Compared with traditional inorganic semiconductors, COFs possess many special advantages for photocatalytic applications:¹⁰ (i) COFs are synthetically accessible with a modular nature, this fact brings the possibility to design targeted structures, modulating their photocatalytic properties by means

of visible-light absorption, and electron-hole separation and transfer; (ii) COFs are able to suppress the fast electron-hole recombination thanks to their highly crystalline and porous structures, decreasing the possibility of charge trapping caused by charged defects;²⁶ (iii) COFs present improved accessibility to catalytic sites due to their large surface area and pore volumes; (iv) Photo-corrosion can be avoided in the robust framework of COFs, which show strong bonds with high chemical and thermal stability; (v) COFs show high charge carrier mobility through the extended π -conjugated structure. These attractive inherent qualities provide COFs with great potential for photocatalytic energy conversion, and they are expected to match or even exceed the performance of conventional photocatalytic inorganic semiconductors.

In this sense, the development of COFs and their heterojunction with inorganic semiconductors has brought great attention for their use as photocatalysts for the production of renewable fuels (*e.g.* H₂).^{27,28} These hybrids are expected to improve charge separation with respect to the inorganic phase by itself and the presence of COFs provides chemical versatility. From this perspective, the design and synthesis of innovative COFs and hybrids thereof are essential. A smart design lead to improved interactions between the organic and the inorganic components and thus, enhanced response in terms of light harvesting and charge separation to boost the photocatalytic activity.

Consequently, the selection of the active site moieties a COF is crucial. Polymers based on boron-centered fluorophores are very interesting materials for photocatalytic conversion of solar energy due to their excellent photophysical properties and high photostability.²⁹ Some of the most outstanding fluorophores reported in the literature belong to the boron dipyrromethene (BODIPY) family of compounds.³⁰ These dyes are composed

of a dipyrromethene bonded to a central BF_2 unit and present an excellent chemical versatility for their use in energy conversion in photovoltaic devices, or hydrogen production.³¹ Furthermore, BODIPY-based CPPs have been used in the design of heterogeneous materials as photocatalysts in organic transformations,^{32,33} hydrogen production and CO_2 photoreduction,³⁴ among others. Also, a BODIPY-based-MOF photocatalyst for hydrogen evolution has been reported.³⁵ However, BODIPY-based COF are scarce³⁶ although several examples exist using BODIPY dye to post-synthetically decorate COFs.^{37–39}

The design of COFs that simultaneously combine crystallinity, stability, and functionality still remain a challenging research area. However, as the COF field grows, new strategies have been developed, facing the crystallinity–stability dichotomy. The reversible bond formation is one of the essential prerequisites for the crystallization of COFs.^{40–42}

Herein, we report the design and synthesis of a non-precedent crystalline and stable enamine linked BODIPY-based COF, named as IEC-1 (IEC stands for IMDEA Energy COF), as an active photocatalyst for hydrogen evolution. The choice of enamine bond and BODIPY core is because they contribute enhancing crystallinity and stability. On one hand, BODIPY is a planar and orthogonal substituted moiety which confers crystallinity and, at the same time BODIPY is a high stable chromophore under illumination. On the other hand, enamine bond not only give high crystallinity but also great chemical stability and robustness. Also, we prepared and scaled-up an organic-inorganic hybrid heterojunction comprising IEC-1 and TiO_2 , which was tested for solar H_2 production at both lab-scale and semi-pilot plant scale. The hybrid IEC-1@T-10 revealed a 2.9-fold improved hydrogen production on semi-pilot plant scale experiments in the absence of any noble metal co-catalyst. The type II charge transfer mechanism in the heterojunction has been elucidated by the combination of optical spectroscopies such as steady state and time-resolved fluorescence as well as transient absorption spectroscopy. Interestingly, these results prove that there are clear evidences of a correlation between the photocatalytic activity of this hybrid, and other related-materials, and their longer transient lifetime.

■ RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design, synthesis and characterization of IEC-1

We decided to design an enamine-based material, due to the demonstrated chemical stability of this kind of linkage in aqueous media.⁴² For this purpose, 1,3,5-Triformylphloroglucinol (Tp) and a diamino-BODIPY monomer (**2**) were selected to form the target COF through the Schiff-base reaction (Figure 1A). Thus, the two monomers react in 2:1 molar relation, first producing the imine condensation, which is followed by an irreversible keto-enol tautomerization to lead the formation of the enamine-type COF (Figure 1A). Synthetic conditions were optimized to obtain high yield as well as high crystallinity IEC-1 (Table S1 and Figure S1 in Supporting Information). The formation of the enamine-type bond was unequivocally confirmed by ^{13}C cross-polarization magic-angle-spinning (CP-MAS) solid-state NMR spectroscopy and Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR):

^{13}C CP-MAS solid-state NMR spectroscopy clearly supports the formation of the IEC-1 in the keto form (Figure 1B). IEC-1 shows signals at 191.3, 182.4 and 175.4 ppm, corresponding to

the carbonyl carbons. These three signals come from the same carbonyl group with three different chemical environments. In the starting material, the aldehyde carbonyl carbon resonance is located near 192.3 ppm (Figure S2). The absence of this peak in the ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectrum indicated the total consumption of the starting materials as well as discard its presence as host molecule. The existence of enamine bond revealed a clear signal centered at 155.9 ppm. The BODIPY's skeleton shows peaks in the region from 149 to 106 ppm and methyl carbon atoms show peaks at 17.5, 13.6 and 11.7 ppm.

FTIR spectra of IEC-1 (Figure S6) also supports the total consumption of the starting materials on the basis of the disappearance of the N–H stretching bands of amino-BODIPY ($\sim 3150\text{--}3080\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the carbonyl stretching band of Tp (1647 cm^{-1}). Interestingly, IEC-1 showed two strong peaks centered at 1618 cm^{-1} and 1544 cm^{-1} , which correspond to the C=O and C=C stretching bands respectively, characteristic of the keto form. Moreover, the FTIR spectra of IEC-1 did not show the characteristic stretching bands of hydroxyl (–OH) functional groups, which should have been present if the compounds existed in the enol form. The decreased value of the C=O stretching frequency is due to the strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding and extended conjugation in the structure. The FTIR spectra of IEC-1 and amino-BODIPY show peaks at 2885 cm^{-1} , which are due to methyl-group C–H stretching.

The crystalline structure of IEC-1 was determined by analysis of powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) data (Figure 1C) and computer modellization. Accordingly, a crystal model was built up based on the formation of honeycomb (**hcb**) layers through the linkage between **TP** and diamino-BODIPY (**2**) building units. Various topologically equivalent models were completed and geometrically optimized with forcefield energy minimization procedures, exploring different stacking sequences of the layers (Figure S7). Their calculated PXRD patterns were compared with the experimental one, and the best agreement was found for a crystal model in the monoclinic $C2$ space group, with lattice parameters values $a = 19.525\text{ \AA}$, $b = 31.234\text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.512\text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 111.07^\circ$, obtained after Pawley refinement (Figure 1C). In this model, the layers are disposed with ABC stacking mode (Figures 1D and 1E), and dichloromethane molecules were incorporated inside the pores, in agreement with the sample washing procedure followed.

Noting that the ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectrum indicates different chemical environments for the carbonyl C atoms (*vide supra*), the disposition of the enamine bonds was fixed accordingly, so that there are three possible scenarios for intralayer hydrogen bond formation between the amine hydrogen atoms and the keto oxygens (Figure S8).

Textural properties were determined; N_2 adsorption and desorption isotherms were measured to evaluate the porosity of IEC-1 (Figure S9). The COF clearly shows the formation of micropores as indicated by a typical type I adsorption isotherm according to IUPAC. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area of the activated COF was found to be $362\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The pore size distribution was calculated with non-local density functional theory (NLDFT). It had narrow pore size distributions of 1.1–1.4 nm exhibiting a maximum at 1.1 nm (Figure S10).

Figure 1. Design, synthesis and characterization of IEC-1

(A) Chemical synthesis of IEC-1.

(B) Solid-state ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR of IEC-1 and the theoretical assignment.

(C) PXRD patterns of IEC-1: experiment (black), Pawley refined (pink), difference (orange), the Bragg positions (green) as well as calculated (blue).

(D) Top view of ABC stacking of IEC-1.

(E) Lateral view of ABC stacking of IEC-1.

(F-G) FESEM images of IEC-1.

(H) Band energy diagram obtained for IEC-1 (TiO_2 is included for comparative proposed), including the water-splitting and MeOH oxidation redox couples at pH = 0. Dotted lines represent the fermi level positions for both materials.

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images (Figure 1F-G and Figure S11) showed that IEC-1 crystallizes with a flower-like morphology, exhibiting a large number of stick-like petals with lengths between 1–10 μm . High resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images also confirm the structural and morphological properties of these samples at the nanoscale (Figure S12).

By combining UV-Vis Spectroscopy, electrochemical and EIS information we can determine the optoelectronic properties of IEC-1. Diffuse reflectance UV-vis absorption confirms that the COF possess an indirect transition with an optical bandgap of 1.75 ± 0.1 eV (Figure S13). Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements (Figure S14) allow to estimate the HOMO (-5.8 eV) and

LUMO (-3.6 eV) energy, according to its oxidation and reduction potentials (0.81 and -1.23 V, respectively), resulting in an electrochemical bandgap of 2.0 ± 0.3 eV. This value is in line with the measured optical band gap, which usually differ between 0.2 or 0.3 eV.^{43,44}

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed at different bias potentials and the Mott-Schottky plot was obtained by calculating the associated capacitance of the electrode-electrolyte interface. This plot allows the determination of the flat band potential that can be associated with the Fermi level energy,^{45,46} which has been determined at a value of 0.77 V vs NHE (Figure S15). This plot also exhibited a negative slope revealing a p-type conductivity of IEC-1.

Photovoltage measurements confirm the photoactive properties of IEC-1, exhibiting the characteristic behaviour of a p-type semiconductor, showing an increase in the signal under illumination (Figure S16A).⁴⁷ The photoresponse of the electrode when illuminating in open circuit potential is 130 mV. Besides, the linear sweep voltammetry measurements under chopped illumination (Figure S16B) confirming the photoactivity of this material and its potential to be used as a photocathode due to the presence of negative photocurrents along the whole potential window.

Hybrid heterojunction IEC-1@TiO₂

The hybrid materials were prepared by wet mixture of IEC-1 and TiO₂ (anatase phase) at different percentage weight of polymer loading, naming the sample as IEC-1@T-x (x=1, 5, 10 and 15 wt. %). PXRD pattern of these hybrid samples are equivalent to that of TiO₂. The highest polymer loaded sample is the only one that present appreciable contributions from IEC- (Inset of Figure S17). ICP analysis confirms the TiO₂ content in the hybrids (Table S2). The corresponding weight percentage of the COF was confirmed by thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) (see Figure S18). In addition, the morphology of the hybrid systems was determined by FESEM (Figure 2) and HRTEM (Figure S19). These images show that the BODIPY-COF is homogeneously covered by the TiO₂ nanocrystals. Surface composition analysis was also determined by XPS. The IEC-1 sample presents a N:F:B (4:2:1) ratio, in good agreement with the corresponding BODIPY stoichiometry (Figure S20A). On the other hand, IEC-1@T-10 sample shows a decrease in the N, F, and B amounts, verifying that TiO₂ mainly covers the COF surface (Figure S20B).

Photocatalytic H₂ production

In a first stage, different sacrificial agents (methanol, ascorbic acid, sodium ascorbate and triethanolamine) were studied at lab scale. The highest activity was obtained with methanol (Table S3) and therefore, it was selected as reductant. Note that the IEC-1 by itself is not active for hydrogen production, but when 1 wt.% of platinum nanoparticles are deposited on its surface shows activity *ca.* 0.07 and 0.08 mmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ (0.02% and 0.03% photonic efficiency) being sodium ascorbate or ascorbic acid the sacrificial agent tested, respectively.

In order to optimize the H₂ production, the polymer loading in the hybrids was optimized at lab-scale in the absence of any noble metal co-catalyst. It was found that the photonic efficiency increases with the amount of polymer loading from 1 wt %, IEC-1@T-1 (ca. 0.06 % ξ), to 10 wt %, IEC-1@T-10 (ca. 0.59% ξ), above which it begins to decrease, IEC-1@T-15 (ca. 0.45% ξ) (Figure S22 and entries 3-6 in Table 1). We found that the best HER performance corresponds to IEC-1@T-10, \approx 1.6 mmol g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹; which was 21-fold higher than TiO₂ (entries 5 and 10, Table 1). The hydrogen production dramatically drops under visible illumination where TiO₂ does not absorb light (Table S4).

The stability of IEC-1@T-10 was evaluated by means of a recyclability experiment consisting on the filtration and redispersion of the photocatalyst. After three reaction cycles (2.5 hours each), the HER values were almost the same (Figure S23A).

Also, the photostability of this sample was studied in a long recycling experiment. First, a photocatalytic HER test was conducted with the fresh sample under 6 hours of UV-vis irradiation. Afterwards, the sample was filtered and re-dispersed to be used in a second cycle of 25 hours of irradiation time. As shown in Figure S23B, the photocatalyst was not deactivated after more than 30 hours of reaction. The structural photostability of IEC-1@T-10 was confirmed after the photocatalytic H₂ production tests by FTIR analyses (Figure S24), Solid-state ¹³C CP/MAS NMR (Figure S25), PXRD (Figure S26), HRTEM (Figure S27) and FESEM (Figure S28).

Table 1. H₂ Production and photonic efficiencies

Entry	Photocatalyst	HER ^a (mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	ξ (%)
1	IEC-1	np ^b	np
2	Pt-1/IEC-1	np	np
3	IEC-1@T-1	0.16	0.06
4	IEC-1@T-5	0.45	0.17
5	IEC-1@T-10	1.61	0.59
6	IEC-1@T-15	1.21	0.45
7	Pt-1/IEC-1@T-10 ^c	32.99	12.21
8	Pt-3/IEC-1@T-10 ^c	49.25	18.23
9	Pt-5/IEC-1@T-10 ^c	50.77	18.79
10	TiO ₂	0.08	0.03
11	Pt-1/TiO ₂	8.90	3.29

^a Lab-scale reaction conditions: 25 mg of catalyst on 130 mL of a methanol aqueous solution (10 vol %) at atmospheric pressure and 20 °C, irradiated by a 150 W medium-pressure Hg immersion lamp

^b np:H₂ not detected

^c Pt-x means platinum loading (x=1, 3 or 5 wt.%). See ICP analysis in Table S2.

Furthermore, we find relevant to compare our result with other COF-based hybrids reported in literature. Remarkably, here we found the highest productions described for a COF-based hybrid photocatalyst in the absence of noble metal co-catalysts (Table S5). For instance, Wang et al. describe an β -ketoenamine-linked COF, namely TpPa-1-COF, with non-noble-metal-based [Mo₃S₁₃]²⁻ nanoclusters which shows a HER of 528 μ mol g⁻¹h⁻¹.²⁸ While, Gao et al. show a hybrid with the same COF and MoS₂ without noble-metal as co-catalyst with 55.85 μ mol g⁻¹h⁻¹ HER.⁴⁸

It is noteworthy that the majority of examples in the literature use platinum as co-catalyst to boost the hydrogen production. Thus, for comparative purposes, we optimized the photodeposition of this metal on our best hybrid (entries 7-9, Table 1). The amount of platinum deposited in each sample was determined by ICP-OES analysis (Table S2) and show concordance with the calculated theoretical amounts. Thus, Pt-3/IEC-1@T-10, substantially increased the HER, reaching 49.25 mmol g cat⁻¹ h⁻¹ (18.23% photonic efficiency). This value is more than 30-times higher than that of the hybrid without Pt, and notably, this is the highest production reported in literature for COFs (Table S5). Further, the performance of this material even surpassed those obtained with TiO₂-based hybrid photocatalysts containing other kind of conductive polymers beyond COFs (Table S6).

Figure 2. Morphological characterization of IEC-1@T-X Hybrid

(A) IEC-1@T-X cartoon: The crystalline IEC-1 is surrounded by TiO₂ nanocrystals.

(B) FESEM panoramic image.

(C) Magnification of the yellow squared region in B. Dashed white line indicates COF location.

(D) X-EDS microanalysis of titanium (green), oxygen (yellow), carbon (red) and boron (purple).

Solar hydrogen production.

The performance of IEC-1@T-10 hybrid was demonstrated under direct solar radiation using a CPC-based photoreactor located at IMDEA Energy (Figure 3A and Figure S29). Figure 3B shows the gas-phase solar hydrogen production from water in the presence of 10 vol% methanol as sacrificial agent. Hydrogen production has been quantified per unit of received energy to make data comparable, considering that the amount of solar radiation may vary between experiments depending on the time of day, season or meteorological conditions. Hydrogen evolution was determined immediately after uncovering the reactor (*i.e.* sharp increase in H₂ production in Figure 3B after the dark stabilization period). A clear correlation was found between received solar irradiance and hydrogen evolution (Figure 3B). Accordingly, cumulative productions showed a good linear correlation with received solar energy (Figure S30) Any thermal contribution to HER was discarded by monitoring H₂ production and temperature evolution in control tests carried out under dark conditions (Figure S31) and H₂ was not detected. These solar reactions exhibit an increase in the H₂ production and electron consumption rate (R_e)³⁴ of 2.9-times for IEC-1@T-10 in comparison to bare TiO₂, and a more than double photonic efficiency, $\xi = 0.24\%$ (Figure 3C). These results correlate well with the higher photocatalytic activity of the hybrid at lab-scale experiments (Figure S22). In terms of energy efficiency, scaling-up tests over IEC-1@T-10 reached 26.5-times higher UV-to-hydrogen efficiency than lab-scale experiments (*ca.* η_{UVTH} of 0.06% and 0.002%, respectively), which supports the successful up-scaling of the hybrid. Besides, the photocatalytic stability of IEC-1@T-10 was further checked over consecutive H₂ evolution tests, just flashing Ar flow (100 mL min⁻¹) for 1 h between experiments. We found a remarkable good stability along 3 recycling tests (Figure 3D), without any catalyst deactivation, demonstrating the robustness of this material under real solar H₂ evolution tests. To the best of our knowledge this is the first scaling-up accomplished by a COF-based hybrid for solar-driven HER (see Table S4 and S5 in SI for reference).

Elucidation of the charge-transfer mechanism

To get insights into the preferential charge dynamics pathways in IEC-1@T-10, we performed spectroscopic studies from the ns to μ s timescale, using both steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence as well as transient absorption spectroscopy (TAS). First, photoluminescence emission of IEC-1@T-10 hybrid was evaluated in solid-state, and compared with that of bare TiO₂ (Figure S32). Under steady-state conditions upon UV light, an apparent quenching of TiO₂ fluorescence was observed due to the presence of the COF. However, the time-resolved fluorescence study (Figure 4A) leads us to conclude that this result was associated with an inner filter effect⁴⁹ instead of a real quenching, since both titania and IEC-1 absorbs light at the excitation wavelength ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm). The fluorescence lifetimes (τ_F) of the hybrids containing different wt.% of polymer (5, 10, 15%) showed a progressive τ_F increase respected to bare TiO₂ (Figure 4A and its fitting curves in Figure S33). Fluorescence interference from IEC-1 is dismissed because IEC-1 does not show fluorescence under these or others excitation conditions.

The Stern Volmer representation (τ/τ_0 vs amount of IEC-1) (Inset of Figure 4A) shows a linear behavior, confirming that the addition of CPP enhances the charge transfer pathway in solid samples. The same behavior was observed employing the reaction media conditions (Figure S34 and its fitting curves in Figure S35). Similar results were previously described for CPPs-based hybrids,^{34,50,51} supporting that the electron transfer from COF's LUMO to the conduction band of TiO₂ (Figure 4E). On the other hand, TAS of IEC-1@T-10 was compared with bare TiO₂ (Figure 4B and 4C). After laser excitation ($\lambda_{exc} = 355$ nm), aqueous TiO₂ suspensions showed a continuous transient absorption (TA) in all spectrum window (Figure 4C, black trace). Here, in presence of methanol (10% v/v) as efficient hole scavenger,⁵²⁻⁵⁴ the temporal profile of TiO₂ at $\lambda_{obs} = 460$ nm showed two main contributions; the first one ($\tau \approx 51$ ns) fitted well to first-order kinetics over the early nanoseconds after the laser

Figure 3. IEC-1@T-10: Scaling up in Solar Reactor

(A) Semi-pilot plant solar CPC reactor and zoom-in of the tubular reactor coated with IEC-1@T-10 hybrid.

(B) Hydrogen evolution rate vs received solar energy, and corresponding solar irradiance (UVA) along the day.

(C) Comparison between cumulative solar hydrogen production (dark blue bars), electron consumption rate (R_e , light blue bars) and photonic efficiencies (ξ , dots) for IEC-1@T-10 and bare TiO₂.

(D) Recyclability study of IEC-1@T-10 hybrid (purple dots) over three consecutive solar HER tests (TiO₂ is included for comparison in grey color).

pulse, followed by a longer second contribution in the μ s time-scale (Figure S36, red trace). On the contrary, using Pt (H_2PtCl_6 in the medium) as an electron acceptor,⁵⁵ a complete quenching of the transients of TiO₂ was observed (Figure S36, blue trace), associated with the reduction of platinum nanoparticles.⁵⁶ These results reveal that the measured TiO₂ nanosecond TAS signal (*ca.* 460-650 nm) under our conditions can be only attributed to photoelectrons.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹

In addition, bare IEC-1 COF showed poor transient absorption under our measurement conditions, accompanied by the practically complete kinetic decay after 300 ns after laser pulse (Figure S37). By analyzing the transient absorption of IEC-1@T-10 hybrid, a 2.9-times increased ΔOD and transient lifetime (τ_{TAS}) was observed during the first 400 ns after pulse with respect to naked TiO₂ (violet traces at Figure 4C, Figure 4D and Figure S38), indicating a decrease in the electron-hole recombination in the presence of the COF. After 3 ms of light exposure, the transient complete disappears in all cases. Interestingly, the lifetime profile of IEC-1@T-10 hybrid exhibited a growth in the first 25 ns after the laser pulse (Figure 4C, inset). This delay in the apparition of the tail clearly indicates that titania has received photogenerated electrons after laser excitation (Figure 4E).

To verify this charge dynamic pathway (Figure 4E), we determine the surface where Pt is photodeposited by means of a reduction pathway. Thus, FESEM studies using a Robinson-type backscatter detector (BED-C) for Z-contrast using the Pt-3/IEC-1@T-10 catalyst depict the preferential deposition of Pt nanoparticles (average size of 2.5 nm) over TiO₂ surface, rather than on the COF (Figure 4D and Figure S39). This was also corroborated by HRTEM (Figure S40). Furthermore, the presence of platinum on the surface was also confirmed by XPS, where Pt is preferentially deposited over TiO₂ with an increase of 3 times (9% wt) respect to the nominal value (3% wt) value (Figure 20C & D). These results are also indicative that the reduction pathway takes place over the TiO₂ surface (Figure 4E). These findings were previously observed in hybrids composed by TiO₂ and conjugated porous polymers based on BOPHY, BODIPY or benzyl functionalized truxene,^{34,50,51} and agree with a type II heterojunction charge transfer mechanism. A comparison among different hybrid systems depicts a clear linear relationship between the transient lifetime and their photocatalytic H₂ production (Figure 4F). Thus, the highest transient lifetime (τ_{TAS}) of IEC-1@T-10 clearly explains their higher photocatalytic activity toward H₂ evolution. These studies demonstrate that TAS experiments can be used as standard methodology to

Figure 4. Charge Transfer Mechanism

(A) Time resolved fluorescence of solid samples measured by time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) technique, decay traces of TiO_2 (grey) and hybrid heterojunction IEC-1@T-10 (violet). Inset: steady state fluorescence spectra $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 300\text{nm}$.

(B) Transient absorption spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355\text{nm}$) for TiO_2 (grey) and IEC-1@T-10 (violet) in deaerated 10 vol% aqueous methanol suspensions at different time scales (20, 100 and 3000 ns after laser pulse).

(C) Transient decay lifetimes ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355\text{nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{mon}} = 460\text{nm}$) for TiO_2 (grey) and IEC-1@T-10 (violet) in deaerated 10 vol% aqueous methanol suspensions. Inset: Expanded image for the first nanoseconds window.

(D) FESEM of Pt-3/IEC-1@T-10 sample where brilliant point are platinum nanoparticles.

(E) Heterojunction charge transfer mechanism for hybrid based on TiO_2 and IEC-1.

(F) Relationship between H_2 production (five hours) from water reactions vs. transient absorption lifetime (τ_{TAS}) for TiO_2 (grey) and hybrid heterojunctions based on BODIPY-COF, IEC-1@T-10 (violet). Other CPP- TiO_2 heterojunctions reported by our group such as those based on BODIPY dyes (CMPBDP@T-10),³⁴ BOPHY dyes (IEP-x@T-10 X=7, 8, 9 and 10)⁵¹ and truxene moiety (TxPP2@T-10)⁵⁰ have been included for comparison and appear in the figure with different colors.

predict the photocatalytic behavior for H₂ production of new hybrid organic inorganic heterojunctions.

■ CONCLUSION

In summary, a novel enamine linked COF based on BODIPY (IEC-1) has been synthesized and fully characterized. The crystal structure of the new BODIPY-based COF has been proposed as consisting of ABC-staked layers. The hybrid material based on TiO₂ as inorganic semiconductor counterpart was prepared to perform the photocatalytic HER. Up-scaled solar-driven HER was successfully accomplished by IEC-1@T-10 in the absence of any noble metal co-catalyst, using a semi-pilot plant gas-phase CPP photoreactor. Under these conditions, this hybrid delivered 2.9-times higher photonic efficiency (ξ) than bare TiO₂ using direct solar light. Remarkably, IEC-1@T-10 hybrid did not show any loss of activity after 3 recycling days. Attending to microscopy and spectroscopic studies, a type II charge transfer mechanism is the responsible for the synergetic effect between IEC-1 and TiO₂. Photophysical studies reveal the longest carrier lifetime (τ_{TAS}) reported until date, as well as a linear correlation between hydrogen production and the transient lifetime of the hybrid in the nanosecond timescale, which clearly explains the high photoactivity of IEC-1@T-10 toward H₂ evolution.

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Author Contributions

M.L. and V.A.P.O. conceived and designed the project. T.N. carried out the design and synthesis of IEC-1. M.G. carried out the photophysical studies. F.G. conducted COF structure analysis. M.B. and T.N. performed the electrochemical and photoelectrochemical measurements. T.N. conducted lab scale photocatalytic hydrogen evolution tests. T.N., L.C. and A.H. performed solar hydrogen evolution experiments. T.N., M.L. and V.A.P.O. wrote the manuscript and discussed the results with all the contributing authors.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. It is made up of General Information, Synthetic Procedures, Powder X-Ray Diffraction spectra, NMR Spectra, FTIR Spectra, XPS Spectra, Structural Modeling, Gas Sorption Studies, FESEM images, HRTEM images, Photochemical Characterization CV measurement, Diffuse Reflectance, Thermo

Gravimetric Analysis, Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Tests and Photocatalytic Hydrogen Production Comparison Tables.

This material is available free of charge at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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